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Research Article

**DEVELOPMENT, CHARACTERIZATION AND
EVALUATION OF COLON SPECIFIC MICRROSPHERES OF
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Abstract:

The objective of the present study was to development, characterization and evaluation of colon specific microspheres of Budesonide. To achieve these objective nine formulations of microspheres were prepared by emulsion solvent evaporation method using Eudragit RS100 and Kollicoat MAE 100 P polymer. Prepared microspheres were evaluated for Particle size analysis, Surface morphology, Differential scanning calorimetric analysis, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy analysis, X-ray diffraction studies, Drug encapsulation efficiency, In-vitro drug release study and Stability study. The microspheres formed have smooth surface and spherical shape as observed in scanning electron microscopy. The drug entrapment efficiency (DEE) of the formulation is in the range of 82.44% to 90.69%. Particle size increases with increasing concentration of polymer, particle size ranging from 4.892 μ m to 5.16 μ m. The Drug-polymer compatibility was studied by using FTIR spectroscopy. The study revealed that there is no interaction between the selected drug and polymers. Differential scanning calorimetry analysis of prepared microspheres indicates that there is no interaction between the drug and polymers. X-ray diffractograms of prepared microspheres indicates that the drug is amorously dispersed in the formulation and enhances the dissolution of the drug. The drug release study was done in simulated gastrointestinal fluids for 2 hrs in gastric fluid (pH 1.2), for 3 hrs in intestinal fluids (pH 6.8) and up to 24hrs in Colonic fluids (pH 7.4) and has shown that the drug was protected from being released in the physiological environment of the stomach and small intestine and efficiency released in Phosphate buffer pH 7.4 (colonic pH). The results showed maximum amount of drug accumulation in colonic pH. Drug release mechanism followed non-Fickian transport. The formulations were found to be stable in short term stability studies.

Keywords:- Budesonide, Colon specific, controlled release, Eudragit RS 100, Kollicoat MAE 100P.

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INTRODUCTION:

Oral Controlled drug delivery system is having greater importance for delivers the drug at a predetermined rate, locally or systemically, for a specified period of time. Controlled release drug delivery employs drug-encapsulating devices from which therapeutic agents may be released at controlled rates for long periods of time, ranging from days to months. Such systems offer numerous advantages over traditional methods of drug delivery, including tailoring of drug release rates, protection of fragile drugs and increased patient comfort and compliance. Controlled drug delivery systems can include the maintenance of drug levels within a desired range, the need for fewer administrations [1].

There are several approaches, which is utilized in achieving colon targeting include use of pH-sensitive polymer, time-dependent formulation, bacterial degrading coating material, biodegradable polymer matrix and hydrogels and prodrug [2].

Microspheres are well designed controlled drug delivery system can overcome some of the problems of conventional therapy and enhance the therapeutic efficacy of the drug [3]. These are the carriers for drug is one such approach which can be used in a sustained controlled release fashion [4].

During the last decade there has been interest in developing site-specific formulations for targeting drug to the colon. Colon was considered as a part of body solely responsible for absorption of water, electrolyte and temporary storage of stools, but now it is accepted as an important site for drug delivery. Targeted delivery ensures the direct treatment at the disease site, lower dosing, and minimizing side effects. Drug targeting to colon is highly desirable for local treatment of a variety of bowel diseases such as ulcerative colitis, Crohn's disease, amoebiasis, colon cancer and systemic delivery of proteins and peptide drugs.

Corticosteroids are often used in the treatment of moderate to severe, active ulcerative colitis; however, they are associated with a wide range of

side-effects. Budesonide is a locally acting corticosteroid, and has highest affinity for glucocorticoid receptor. It is approved as a standard drug for the localized treatment of inflammatory bowel disorder due to negligible oral bioavailability, rapid clearance and no active metabolites. To improve the specificity of drug release in the colon, enzymatically controlled delivery systems containing polysaccharides are widely used [5].

The objective of the study is to formulate and develop colon targeted drug delivery system of Budesonide microspheres by using Eudragit RS 100 and Kollicoat MAE 100P as a pH sensitive polymer. By directly targeting the drug to colon, the maximum concentration of drug reaches and increases the residence time of drug in colon with an improved patient compliance, lesser side effects and an ideal drug delivery system [2].

MATERIALS AND METHODS:**Materials:-**

Budesonide was obtained from Aarthi Pharma, Mumbai. Eudragit RS100 obtained from Yarrow Chem Products, Mumbai. Kollicoat MAE 100P was obtained from Sigma-aldrich. All reagents and chemical used were of analytical grade.

Methods:-**Formulation of Budesonide Microspheres:-**

Budesonide microspheres were prepared using Eudragit RS 100, Kollicoat and PVA (Polyvinyl alcohol) as continuous phase by solvent evaporation technique. Initially dichloromethane (DCM) and methanol was mixed uniformly at room temperature, then Eudragit RS 100 and Kollicoat in 1:1 ratio was dissolved in the above solution. To this mixture, 100mg of Budesonide was added, mixed thoroughly and injected drop wise in to aqueous solution of PVA (0.5% w/v, 200ml) through a 22G needle at 30-40°C and the resultant o/w type emulsion was stirred on a mechanical stirrer at 1200 rpm for 1hr. The microspheres obtained was washed for 2-3 times with distilled water and dried at room temperature. Different concentrations and ratios of polymers used in the formulation of microspheres are mentioned in **Table 01**[6, 7].

Table 01: Different ratios of polymers used in the formulation of Budesonide microspheres

Formulation	Budesonide	Eudragit	Kollicoat	Methanol	Dichloromethane
BDS 1	100	0.5		10	10
BDS 2	100	1.0		10	10
BDS 3	100	1.5		10	10
BDS 4	100	2.0		10	10
BDS 5	100		0.5	10	10
BDS 6	100		1.0	10	10
BDS 7	100		1.5	10	10
BDS 8	100		2.0	10	10
BDS 9	100	1.0	1.0	10	10

Evaluation of Microspheres:-**Particle size and Zeta potential analysis:-**

The prepared colon specific microspheres were evaluated for particle size and zeta potential were determined by photon correlation spectroscopy (PCS) using Malvern particle size analyser 2000 HS. The samples were prepared by applying suitable dilution. The size measurement was performed in triplicate at room temperature [8].

Scanning electron microscopic studies:-

The shape and surface morphology of Budesonide microspheres and Eudragit coated microspheres were investigated using Scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The samples for SEM study were prepared by lightly sprinkling the formulation on a double-adhesion tape stuck to an aluminium stub. The stubs were then coated with gold to a thickness of 300 Å under an argon atmosphere using a gold sputter module in a high vacuum evaporator. The coated samples were then randomly scanned and photo micrographs were taken with a scanning electron microscope [9].

Differential scanning calorimetric analysis:-

Thermograms of the samples were obtained by a Perkin-Elmer differential scanning calorimeter (Pyris 6 DSC, software Pyris manager, Perkin-Elmer Schweiz AG, Hunenberg, Switzerland). Samples of 3 mg were accurately weighed into aluminum pans and then hermetically sealed with aluminum lids. The thermograms of samples were obtained at a scanning rate of 10°C/min over a temperature range of 50 to 350°C [10].

Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy analysis:-

The Fourier Transformed Infrared spectroscopic analysis (FT-IR) is done to study the polymer- drug interactions and the physical state of drug in the microsphere. The FT-IR of pure drug, empty microspheres, and the drug loaded microspheres is done separately to judge accurately [11].

X-ray diffraction studies:-

PXRD patterns were obtained using X'Pert PRO MRD® (PANalytical Ltd., Almelo, and the Netherlands) with Cu Kα radiation generated at 200 mA and 45 kV. The samples were placed on a silicon plate at room temperature and 2θ scans were collected from 5° to 60°C [12].

Drug encapsulation efficiency:-

Weighed amount of microspheres (100mg) with phosphate buffer pH 7.4 (10 ml) was added in a vial. The solution was stirred vigorously for 24 hours

with mechanical stirrer. Supernatant was collected by centrifugation and drug content in supernatant was determined by using UV spectrophotometer at wavelength 244.8nm. Efficiency of drug entrapment is calculated by the following formula [9].

$$\text{DEE} = \frac{\text{absorbance} \times \text{dilution factor}}{\text{Slope}}$$

$$= \text{concentration} \times \text{dilution factor}$$

$$\text{DEE} = \frac{\text{drug content}}{\text{Label claim}} \times 100$$

In-vitro drug release study:-

The *in-vitro* release studies of drug-loaded microspheres were carried out in simulated gastric fluids. Microspheres (100 mg) were weighed accurately and gently spread over the surface of 900 ml of dissolution medium (SGF). The content was rotated at 100 rpm at 37±0.5°C. Perfect sink condition was maintained during drug dissolution study period. The simulation of GI transit condition was achieved by altering the pH of dissolution medium at different time intervals. The pH of dissolution medium was maintained at 1.2 for 2hrs. Using 0.1N HCl and then 3 hrs using pH 6.8 phosphate buffer. The release study was observed by adjusting the pH 2nd hour the pH of the dissolution medium was adjusted to 7.4 and maintained up to 24 hours. A 5-ml sample was withdrawn from the dissolution medium at various time intervals using a pipette and analyzed drug release using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer at 244.8nm. The receptor volume was maintained constant by replacing with equivalent volume of buffer after each withdrawal [13].

Stability study:-

The purpose of stability study is to provide evidence on how the quality of the drug substance or drug product varies with time under the influence of a variety of environmental factors such as temperature, humidity and light. The Budesonide loaded microspheres formulation was filled in tightly closed glass vials and subjected to short term stability testing according to the international conference on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines for zone 3 and 4. The packed containers of microspheres were kept at room temperature (25±2°C) and acceleration condition (40±2°C/75±5%RH) in a hot air oven for a period for one month. The sample (n=9) were analysed at 45 days and evaluated for drug content [14].

Results and Discussion:-**Particle size and Zeta potential analysis:-**

The particle size determination of the Microspheres was carried out by using particle size analyzer

(Malvern). The particle size of the prepared microspheres was found to be in the range of 4.892 μm to 5.16 μm . As the concentration of the polymers increases the size of the microspheres increased. .

The results are given in **Table 02**. Zeta potential determination was found to be -27.7. This indicates that the drug was stable in formulations. The results are given in **Fig 01**.

TABLE 02: Average size of the Budesonide microspheres.

Microspheres code	Average size (μm)
BDS1	4.892
BDS2	5.032
BDS3	5.056
BDS4	5.103
BDS5	4.92
BDS6	5.039
BDS7	5.099
BDS8	5.12
BDS9	5.16

FIGURE 1: Zeta potential distribution of Budesonide microspheres

Scanning electron microscopic studies:-

The prepared microspheres were studied under scanning electron microscope (SEM) to observe the surface morphology and shape of the formulations. The SEM reveals that the prepared microspheres was spherical shape, smooth surface and free flowing in nature. The results are given in **Fig 02**.

FIGURE 02: Scanning electron microscopic photographs of BDS4(a), BDS8(b), BDS9(c) Microspheres.

Differential scanning calorimetric analysis:-

The DSC analysis is the most widely used to characterize the physical state of drug in the formulations. The DSC thermograms of Budesonide exhibited a single sharp endothermic peak at 260.32°C due to melting transition point of drug. The drug free microspheres have exhibited endothermic peak at 72°C and 189°C, and drug containing formulation (BDS9) exhibited peak at 64.26°C and 189.93°C in the DSC thermogram. There is no melting peak of drug at 260°C appeared in thermogram indicating the complete dispersion of drug in the carrier polymer due to phase transition. This indicates that there is no interaction between the drug and polymers. The results are given in Fig 03.

FIGURE 03: DSC Thermograms of Budesonide (a), Dummy BDS9 (b) and drug loaded BDS9 Microspheres(c).

Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy analysis:-

FT-IR spectroscopy was carried out in order to investigate the possible interaction between drug and selected polymers. IR spectrum for pure drug and physical mixture of drug-polymers were obtained and characterized. The intense peak at 3490 cm^{-1} is shown due to O-H stretching. 2932 cm^{-1} is shown due to C-H stretching. 1719 & 1664 cm^{-1} is shown due to C=O stretching. FTIR spectra of pure Budesonide drug and physical mixture showed corresponding peaks which indicating no interaction between polymers and drug Budesonide. The results are given in the Fig 04.

FIGURE 04: FTIR spectra of Budesonide (a), Dummy BDS9 (b) and drug loaded BDS9 Microspheres(c).

X-ray diffraction studies:-

The X-ray diffractograms of pure drug Budesonide, drug free microspheres (dummy) and drug loaded microspheres (BDS9) and Budesonide shown 2 θ characteristic intense peak between 6.2°, 12.2°, 15.6°, 16.1° and 24° representing higher crystalline nature. Some of the crystalline peaks of the drug were still detectable in the formulation but with reduce the intensity and less number in the diffractograms. This indicates that the drug is amorphously dispersed in the formulation and enhances the dissolution of the drug **Fig 05**.

FIGURE 05: X-Ray Diffractograms of Budesonide (a), Dummy BDS9 (b) and drug loaded BDS9 Microspheres (c).

Drug encapsulation efficiency:-

The drug entrapment efficiency (DEE) of the formulation is in the range of 82.44% to 90.69%. And BDS9 formulation also shows highest entrapment efficiency (90.69 %). Which may be due to increased polymer weight ratio, as a result the drug entrapment efficiency increases. The results are given in **Table 03**.

Table 03: Drug encapsulation efficiency (DEE) of the Budesonide microspheres.

Microspheres code	DEE
BDS1	83.51±0.7
BDS2	90.69±1.3
BDS3	82.44±1.9
BDS4	84.44±0.25
BDS5	84.39±0.7
BDS6	89.07±1.3
BDS7	83.63±1.6
BDS8	86.60±1.6
BDS9	89.91±0.01

In-vitro drug release study:-

The *in-vitro* dissolution study of microspheres was performed by using type 2 dissolution test apparatus in 0.1N Hcl pH 1.2 (upper GIT), phosphate buffer 6.8pH and phosphate buffer pH 7.4 (gastrointestinal pH) by using cellophane membrane. The results of *in-vitro* dissolution studies are shown in the **Fig 06**. The cumulative percentage of drug release from BDS1 to BDS9 formulations ranges from 78.98% to 95.42%. The combination of Eudragit RS100 and kollicoat MAE100 P in the formulation retard drug release in gastric pH and intestinal pH about 13.07% of drug within 5 hours, due to the pH-sensitive polymer coating and maximum amount of drug was release in phosphate buffer pH 7.4 (colonic pH) about 78.98% because the polymers are being soluble around pH

7.0 which leads to the formation of pores in the coating layer which allows medium to release the drug, ruptures the outer coat and prolonged drug release.

FIGURE 06: *In-vitro* drug release of Budesonide from BDS1 to BDS9 Microspheres in phosphate buffer 7.4pH

In-vitro release kinetics:-

The release kinetics was evaluated by making use of Zero order, First order, Higuchi's and Korsmeyer-Peppas's equations. The drug release through the microspheres of Budesonide follows Zero order kinetics with controlled release mechanism, by fitting in the Korsmeyer-Peppas's equation, the release kinetics follows non-Fickian kinetics. The range of 'n' value for Korsmeyer-Peppas's equation -1 to 1. If the 'n' values of Korsmeyer-Peppas's equation is below 0.5, which indicates Fickian kinetics. If the 'n' value of Korsmeyer-Peppas's equation is in between 0.5 to 1, this indicates non-Fickian kinetics. The prepared microspheres of budesonide release kinetics fitted in Korsmeyer-Peppas's equation. 'n' values are in between 0.5 to 1, so the release is following non-Fickian, controlled release mechanism. The results are shown in the **Table 04**.

TABLE 04: Regression analysis of the *In-vitro* drug release data of Budesonide microspheres according to release kinetic models.

Formulation n code	Zero order		First order		Higuchi	Korsmeyer's	
	N	R ²	N	R ²	R ²	N	R ²
BDS1	4.245	0.954	0.165	0.8643	0.822	0.752	0.911
BDS2	3.529	0.991	0.154	0.9015	0.827	0.574	0.909
BDS3	3.286	0.964	0.146	0.8986	0.819	0.453	0.965
BDS4	3.158	0.947	0.14	0.9026	0.967	0.723	0.970
BDS5	3.214	0.944	0.175	0.8946	0.820	0.645	0.971
BDS6	3.145	0.947	0.167	0.8959	0.828	0.862	0.960
BDS7	3.443	0.941	0.15	0.8959	0.950	0.797	0.982
BDS8	3.279	0.975	0.143	0.8959	0.815	0.816	0.969
BDS9	3.396	0.977	0.106	0.8643	0.803	0.870	0.975

Stability study:-

The short term stability studies were carried out as per ICH guidelines for the most satisfactory formulation BDS9 at two different temperature conditions, that is, refrigeration temperature (2-4°C) and room temperature (RT) (27-30°C) for a period of 45 days to assess short term stability as per ICH guidelines. At fixed time, the formulation was evaluated for drug content and *in-vitro* drug profile. Drug content study shows there is no significant change in drug content. *In-vitro* drug release profile was found to super impossible with the initial results shows in **Table 05**. Therefore the BDS9 formulation is stable.

TABLE 05: Drug entrapment efficiency and Drug release study after Stability Study.

Formulation	Percentage of Drug entrapment efficiency	
	Before stability test	After stability test
F9	89.91±0.01%	88.76±0.012

Formulation	Percentage drug release	
	Before stability test	After stability test
F9	78.98±0.01	78.67±0.031

CONCLUSION:

The preformulation studies involving description of solubility, melting point, of the drug and evaluated for various parameters. The colon specific microspheres of Budesonide were prepared by emulsion solvent evaporation method by using polymers, such as Eudragit RS100 and kollicoat MAE100 P. The combination of two polymers shows better retardation efficiency release of drug in a controlled manner. *In-vitro* drug release study of the BDS9 formulation about 13.07% of drug within 5 hours, and maximum amount of drug was release in phosphate buffer pH 7.4 (colonic pH) about 78.98%. However by the pharmacokinetic studies it indicates that *in-vitro* drug release of the formulations follows zero order kinetics and the mechanism followed non-Fickian kinetics. The formulations were found to be stable in short term stability studies.

From the results it indicates that biocompatible and cost effective polymers like Eudragit RS 100 and kollicoat MAE 100 P can be used to formulate efficient microspheres with good percentage entrapment efficiency and controlled release up to 24 hr in 7.4pH phosphate buffer. Hence these microspheres of budesonide can be targeted to colon. By the study it can be suggested that there is further scope for *in-vivo* and pharmacokinetic study.

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